

Investigation of the properties of humic acids of coal sludge from the Inta Mining and Processing Plant

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Coal sludge is formed during the coal enrichment process. It contains both organic and mineral parts. The main problem in the processing of coal sludge is its high ash content (up to 80%) and fine dispersion (particle size is less than 1 mm).

The Inta coals include humic acids, are of a low carbonification degree. They are complex by petrographic composition. The coals are characterised by high ash content – 21.3–39% and low sulfur content – 2.17–3.35%. The study material was coal sludge taken from the sludge storage of the Kapitalnaya mine. Coal was extracted from a well down to a depth of 9 m. The samples were numbered from top to bottom, the sample core was divided into one-meter sections.

Humic acid salts were obtained by the Tyurin method [1]. The obtained sample of the humic acid (HA) preparation was identified for the content of hydroxyl (aliphatic and phenolic) and carboxyl groups, the content of which was 5.3%, 9.0% and 1.3%, respectively. Phenolic and carboxyl groups play the most significant role in aromatic structures, since they determine the ability of humic acids to bind to complexes with heavy metals [2]. This fact is of great interest of we consider the concentration of isotopes of uranium and other radionuclides. By our studies, humic acids (HA) extracted from coal sludge sorbed 47.6% of uranium from the solution with the sorption capacity 6.7 µg/g sorbent and the amount of bound uranium 3.5 µg/g sorbent.

To assess the effect of the humic preparation on agricultural plants, we performed phyto-testing with seeds of spring oats (*Avena sativa* L.). Phyto-testing was carried out in accordance with GOST 12038-84 [3].

By the obtained results, there are several different patterns of HA effects on the germination rate of spring oat seeds (*Avena sativa* L.). For example, low HA concentrations (0.005–0.025%) stimulated seed germination by 25–27% (germination energy). HA concentrations of more than 0.5% strongly inhibited the germination process of oat seeds. Germination in this case was no more than 50%. Thus, HAs can have either a stimulating effect on plants or act as a herbicide at high concentrations.

References

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